

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Health
OFFICE OF THE SECRETARY

MAR 14 2018

ADMINISTRATIVE ORDER

No. 2018 - 0010

SUBJECT: Interim Guidelines on Health Financing for Medical Needs of Dengvaxia Vaccinees

I. BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE

The CYD-Tetravalent Dengue Vaccine (Dengvaxia) was first introduced in the country through a school-based immunization program to public elementary school students nine years old and above, in the National Capital Region (NCR), Region 3, and Region 4A. It was then followed by a community-based immunization program in Cebu Province of Region 7 and in NCR. More than 830,000 individuals were vaccinated in these programs, in addition to those vaccinated by the private sector.

On November 29, 2017, Sanofi Pasteur released an update based on analysis of long-term clinical studies, which confirmed the vaccine's persistent protective benefit against severe and hospitalized dengue in seropositive individuals. However, for seronegative individuals, there may be an increased risk of severe or hospitalized dengue, upon subsequent dengue infection, in the longer-term.

This development raised public concerns regarding Dengvaxia, which prompted the Department of Health (DOH) to suspend the school- and community-based dengue immunization programs. To address the fears of the public, the DOH offered free medical services to Dengvaxia vaccinees, who will experience signs/symptoms of dengue, or other adverse events that may occur during the enhanced surveillance and monitoring period.

This Administrative Order outlines the health financing and payment mechanisms for the medical needs of Dengvaxia vaccinees. It aims to ensure timely and equitable access to healthcare services among the vaccinees.

II. Objectives

General Objective:

To provide financing and payment mechanisms that would meet the medical needs of Dengvaxia vaccinees who exhibit signs and/or symptoms of dengue infection or adverse events related to the vaccination within the enhanced surveillance and monitoring period.

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Specific Objectives:

1. To guide DOH Central and Regional Offices (ROs), PhilHealth, Local Government Units (LGUs), and other public and private institutions on the financing mechanisms and procedures to cover the medical needs of Dengvaxia vaccinees who consult or seek treatment at government health facilities and private hospitals.
2. To guide national and local government health facilities, including health centers/rural health units (RHUs), infirmaries and hospitals, and private hospitals on financing arrangements that would cover the medical needs of Dengvaxia vaccinees.
3. To provide a basis for advisories that will inform families of Dengvaxia vaccinees on the financing arrangements to cover the medical needs of the vaccinees in government health facilities or private hospitals.

III. Scope and Coverage

This order shall apply to government health facilities, as defined in Section IV.5 of this Order, and private hospitals nationwide.

It shall cover Dengvaxia vaccinees under the DOH school-based and community-based programs who seek consultation or health services at government health facilities or private hospitals for suspected dengue or adverse events, if any, which may arise within the enhanced surveillance and monitoring period.

IV. Definition of Terms

The following terms and acronyms shall be defined as follows:

1. **No Balance Billing (NBB)** – refers to a PhilHealth policy that means no other fees or expenses shall be charged to or paid for by an eligible patient-member above and beyond PhilHealth package rates in PhilHealth accredited facilities (PhilHealth Circular 2017-0017);
2. **Medical Assistance to Indigent Patients Program (MAIP Program)** – refers to the program established by the DOH to support and augment other financing schemes in subsidizing the medical expenses of indigent and poor patients;
3. **Point-of-Service Enrollment (POS)** - refers to the program provided in the General Appropriations Act to cover all Filipinos, whether unregistered or inactive, registered members especially those who are financially incapable (PhilHealth Circular 2017-0025);
4. **Case Rate** – refers to the fixed rate or amount that PhilHealth will reimburse for a specific illness/ case, which shall cover for the fees of health care professionals, and all facility charges including, but not limited to, room and board, diagnostics and laboratories, drugs, medicine and supplies, operating room fees, and other fees and charges. The PhilHealth case rates for dengue are as follows:
 - a. Php 16,000 for severe dengue;
 - b. Php 10,000 for dengue without warning signs or dengue with warning signs in Level 1 to 3 hospitals; and,
 - c. Php 7,000 for dengue without warning signs or dengue with warning signs in infirmaries;

5. **Government Health Facilities** – refer to barangay health stations, health centers, City Health Offices, Rural Health Units (RHUs), infirmaries, DOH-retained hospitals, Local Government Unit (LGU) hospitals, other government hospitals;
6. **Selected Private Hospitals** – PhilHealth-accredited private hospitals that have agreed to enter into a Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) with DOH and/or its ROs for NBB and/or the MAIP program; and
7. **Primary Care Benefit 1 (PCB 1) Package** – refers to primary care benefits package which includes the following 3 main provisions (PhilHealth Circular 10 s., 2012):
 - a. primary preventive services;
 - b. diagnostic examinations; and,
 - c. drugs and medicines.

V. General Guidelines

1. Dengvaxia vaccinees under the DOH school-based and community-based dengue immunization program, shall be entitled to applicable health financing and payment arrangements that would cover medical services at government health facilities and private hospitals within the next 5 years, at the minimum, enhanced surveillance and monitoring period.
2. Dengvaxia vaccinees shall be accommodated in dengue/Dengvaxia fast lanes that have been established and are being maintained in government health facilities and private hospitals.
3. Dengvaxia vaccinees who avail of outpatient services in government health facilities shall be covered by the regular budgetary appropriation of said facilities, as well as the augmented commodity, logistics, and other support from the DOH.
4. Dengvaxia vaccinees who avail of in-patient services in government health facilities shall be covered by the applicable PhilHealth benefit package, and the NBB scheme.
5. Dengvaxia vaccines who are not covered by PhilHealth shall be enrolled through the POS.
6. Dengvaxia vaccinees who avail of in-patient services in hospitals (i.e. PhilHealth-accredited government and private hospitals) shall be entitled to the PhilHealth benefit package with case payment based on the final diagnosis.
7. As per a MOA between and among the DOH, the Philippine Hospital Association (PHA), the Association of Hospital Administrators (AHA), the Private Hospitals Association of the Philippines, Inc (PHAPi), and the Philippine Medical Association (PMA), private hospitals and practitioners that are members of the said organizations are obliged to provide NBB services to Dengvaxia vaccinees; *Provided that*, in case the vaccinee is found to be suffering from some other medical conditions not covered by PhilHealth, the expenses shall be borne by the MAIP program, based on existing guidelines and criteria.
8. The DOH ROs shall enter into MOAs with government health facilities like LGU hospitals and State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) hospitals, and selected private hospitals in accordance with the MAIP program guidelines and/or

- negotiate NBB that would be made available to Dengvaxia vaccinees who would experience dengue signs and symptoms or other adverse events that may arise within the enhanced surveillance and monitoring period.
9. For expenses not covered by the PhilHealth case rate, Dengvaxia vaccinees can avail of the MAIP program in government health facilities and selected private hospitals, subject to existing guidelines and criteria.
 10. The list of government health facilities and private hospitals that have entered into MOAs with the DOH and/or its ROs shall be made known to the public.
 11. The masterlist of Dengvaxia vaccinees shall be provided to the concerned PhilHealth Regional Offices for cross-checking of claims and other related purposes.

VI. Specific Guidelines

A. PhilHealth enrollment of Dengvaxia vaccinees

1. Government health facilities and private hospitals shall determine whether or not a Dengvaxia vaccinee is a PhilHealth member or dependent for purposes of processing PhilHealth claims.
2. Government health facilities shall facilitate the PhilHealth enrollment of Dengvaxia vaccinees who are not PhilHealth member/dependent through the POS.
3. POS enrollment of Dengvaxia vaccinees by private hospitals shall be subject to existing PhilHealth guidelines on POS.
4. Dengvaxia vaccinees accessing health services at barangay health stations, health centers, and RHUs shall be required to submit the following documentary requirements:
 - i. Duly accomplished PhilHealth Member Registration Form; and,
 - ii. Copy of Dengvaxia ID card.

The foregoing shall be immediately forwarded by the Municipal/City Health Officers to the concerned PhilHealth Regional Offices.

B. Payment scheme applicable for Dengvaxia vaccines accessing health services:

1. Government health facilities shall provide out-patient care to Dengvaxia vaccinees for suspected dengue cases in the form of consultation and free laboratory examinations, such as, NS1 antigen screening test, CBC; *Provided that*, the Dengvaxia vaccinees shall be referred to a facility with complete laboratory capability in case the required services are not available in the referring hospital; *Provided further that*, the following rules shall also be applied:
 - a. If the patient has been assessed to have dengue without warning signs, and advised for outpatient/home care, the PhilHealth PCB 1 package shall apply, subject to existing PhilHealth guidelines on PCB 1 package; and,
 - b. If the patient needs to be referred to a higher-level facility for further assessment, or possible admission, the referring facility shall provide the necessary assistance.

2. Government health facilities shall provide in-patient care to Dengvaxia vaccinees in accordance with the following rules:
 - a. If the final diagnosis is dengue, patient shall be entitled to the following:
 - i. NBB; and,
 - ii. PhilHealth case rate for dengue as defined in Section IV.4 of this Order;
 - b. If the final diagnosis is not dengue, patient shall be entitled to the following:
 - i. NBB; and,
 - ii. PhilHealth case rate applicable for the final diagnosis
3. Private hospitals shall provide in-patient care in accordance with the following rules:
 - a. If the final diagnosis is dengue, patient shall be entitled to the applicable PhilHealth case rate, as defined in Section IV.4 of this Order.
 - b. If the final diagnosis is not dengue, patient shall be entitled to the case rate applicable for the final diagnosis.
 - c. For selected private hospitals, as defined in Section IV.6, the patient shall be covered according to the MOA for NBB and/or MAIP program, subject to existing guidelines and criteria.

VII. Effectivity

This Order shall be effective immediately.

FRANCISCO T. DUQUE III, MD, MSc
Secretary of Health

Annex:

Table 1: Summary of Health Financing Mechanisms for Dengvaxia Vaccinees

		Health Facilities	
		Government Health Facilities	Private Health Facilities
Dengvaxia Vaccinees	In-patient (Hospital-based care)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular budget • PhilHealth Case Rate Payment based on final diagnosis • NBB • MAIP program (subject to existing criteria/guidelines) <p>*Point-of service enrolment for vaccinees not previously covered by PhilHealth (subject to existing PhilHealth guidelines on POS)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PhilHealth Case Rate Payment based on final diagnosis • NBB and/or MAIP program for private PhilHealth-accredited hospitals that have entered into a MOA with DOH and/or its ROs <p>*Point-of service enrolment for vaccinees not previously covered by PhilHealth, subject to existing PhilHealth guidelines on POS</p>
	Outpatient (Hospital OPD and Health Center/RHU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular Budget of Health Centers/ RHU/ Infirmaries/ Hospitals • Augmented support from DOH (i.e., commodities, logistics, drugs and medicines, and other support) • PCB 1 package (as applicable, for PCB 1-accredited facilities) 	